

DEVELOPMENT OF STUDENTS' MUSICAL ABILITIES BASED ON INDIVIDUAL APPROACH

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Abstract: In this article, there is a scientific debate about the nature of organizing the educational process based on an individual approach to the development of students' musical abilities in music culture classes. Also, the article describes the implementation of the scientific-theoretical and practical methodology of teaching in the educational process based on an individual approach and its importance. It is known that the formation of musical abilities in the young generation is very important for the society, because in order to form a cultural and aesthetic worldview in the future generation, it is necessary to form their musical abilities first.

Key words: Music education, pedagogical diagnosis, musical ability, methodology, individual approach, educational system, aesthetic education, skills, music pedagogy.

Introduction:

The art of music, which has a direct and strong influence on a person, occupies a great place in the general cultural development of a person. Music is a constant companion of a person throughout his life. According to the French writer Stendhal, the art of music is the only art that penetrates so deeply into the human soul that it can even describe the experience of his thoughts. Many writers, composers, musicologists, teachers, in their thoughts about the formation of a harmoniously developed personality, pay attention to the fact that its component is work on musical and aesthetic education, which makes sense only if there is a quality of consistency. Working with children in the process of musical and aesthetic education is of particular importance. This is the foundation, without which musical education, training and education will never bring full results.

The main part.

Music is close to the emotional nature of the child. Music lessons are of great importance for personality formation, development of emotional and creative inclinations in children. Under the influence of music, his artistic perception develops, experiences become richer. In the process of education and training, it is necessary to pay enough attention to the musical development of children, to the formation of their interest and love for music. Formed during childhood has a great influence on the subsequent emotional development of a person. Music has a stimulating effect on the intellectual formation of a person, has a beneficial effect on the moral education of a person, forms internal discipline and natural sensitivity, and also distracts the unstable psyche of a child from dangerous hobbies. In addition, science has proven that the development of musical abilities has a positive effect on the development of general abilities.

Musical and aesthetic education is not to provide children with knowledge and skills in the field of musical art, but to develop creative activity, independence of each child, to form

his educational interests, and a positive motivation to get acquainted with music. All this can be achieved only by taking into account the individual capabilities and characteristics of the child. The above-mentioned tasks are intended to be fulfilled by the system of additional music education for children, which is now widely developed in the society, which includes art schools, music and choir schools.

Most representatives of the modern music and pedagogic community are convinced that relying on an individual approach to teaching is the only and main way to increase the effectiveness of musical education and upbringing of children. Modern music pedagogy is based on the idea that all children can be taught music, that musical abilities can be developed, even at the beginning stage. A completely new scientific context is being developed in the field of modern music pedagogy. One of the most important points of projection of this context to the problems of music pedagogy is musical ability. If the development of a person's musical abilities starts from a very early childhood, it will positively affect the formation of his personality.

Literature analysis (review).

The psychological and pedagogical foundations of musical and aesthetic upbringing and education of children are well-known representatives of music pedagogy and psychology B. M. Teplov, A. G. Rubinshtein [5, p. 41], L. A. Barenboym, K. N. Igumnov [6, p. 23], G. G. Neygauz, K. V. Tarasov and reflected in the works of others. In recent decades, the theoretical basis of modern musical and pedagogical research has been significantly expanded by the works of scientists who have been engaged in the development of this problem in society.

Debate.

Emphasizing the positive movement in the field of musical psychology and pedagogy, it should be noted that in the field of musical and pedagogical practice, the scientific forms, methods and means of developing musical abilities, taking into account the individual characteristics of children, are not sufficiently developed and scientifically supported. remains. In such a situation, understanding and practical development of new approaches to the process of music education becomes relevant.

In pedagogy textbooks, individual approach is considered as one of the most important principles of education and training. Individual approach means orientation to individual psychological characteristics of the student, selection and application of appropriate methods and methods, various options of tasks, dose of homework. This is a didactic principle that makes adjustments to the organization of the educational process. It is a very old tradition to take into account the individual characteristics of a child of primary school age in the educational process. The need for this is clear, because elementary school students differ significantly from each other in various indicators.

The teacher should know the individual characteristics of each student, the level of development of musical hearing, sense of rhythm, level of musical memory, temperament and character traits. Among the individual musical abilities of a person, performing data has a special place, which not only determines the suitability of the child's physical parameters for this musical instrument, but also the presence of artistry, that is, the love of public performances, the behavior of a person on stage, the reaction of the audience also means the relationship.

A necessary condition for the successful implementation of an individual approach to teaching is the pedagogical tactics of the teacher, a calm tone of addressing the child, a word

of encouragement, approval for a successful answer, a beautifully executed tone is more than harsh words results. A student, especially a weak one, must be sure that the teacher is interested in his achievements, sees any, even the smallest, progress and is happy with it. These general rules are especially important in the individual approach to the child, they should not reduce the demand for the student.

The next important condition for implementing an individual approach to the student is education aimed at forming the personality of the student. This includes effective attention to the creative individuality of each student in each lesson. First of all, it is necessary to educate children's interest in lessons, academic work and responsible attitude.

Implementation of an individual approach to education of schoolchildren is a dynamic process that continues along with the development and change of the child, his level of knowledge, the formation of skills and abilities, the development and change of interests and inclinations. Accordingly, the goals, content, and methods of approaching the child will change. Therefore, it is important to see the prospects of development of students and the prospects of working with them. It should be noted that each child really needs an individual approach, because this is an indispensable condition and condition for the formation of a harmonious and well-developed personality, the formation of a person as a unique individuality. The implementation of a personal approach includes not only the teacher's personal contact with the student, but also the indirect influence on the student through the children's team, the student's family.

A personal approach gives good results only if the work is carried out not only systematically, but also according to a certain plan. Private lessons are designed to interest children and engage them in music. The main purpose of such lessons is to master the skills and abilities acquired in music lessons, to develop musical abilities in children: memory, sense of rhythm, listening to music. The individual approach of the teacher to the student, as well as the choice of repertoire depends on age, individual character traits, musical and intellectual abilities. The successful development of individual abilities of students is possible when the educational process is organized as an intensive intellectual activity taking into account the unique characteristics and capabilities of each child, only by knowing the needs, interests, level of preparation, knowledge characteristics of the student, you can gain knowledge. , you can create optimal conditions for mastering skills and abilities, developing abilities.

Individual approach to schoolchildren is the most important principle of education and upbringing. Its implementation involves the temporary change of the closest tasks and specific aspects of the content of educational work, the permanent change of its methods and organizational forms, taking into account the general and unique characteristics of the personality of each student. includes An individual approach to the educational process means effective attention to each student, his creative individuality in the lesson system of compulsory curricula, frontal, group and individual in order to improve the quality of each student's learning and development. includes a judicious combination of lessons. As A. Gottsdiner noted in his work: "huge, still undiscovered resources for musical education are hidden in the combination of individual and collective education in various ensembles" [4, p. 45].

Thus, the development of musical abilities of elementary school students based on an individual approach will be effective if:

- the individual-personal factor is taken into account in the learning process;

- development of musical abilities of young students is carried out in the process of musical and creative activity;
- the principle of unification of performance, game, theater activities is used for the development of creative skills in musical development.

Summary:

Thus, primary school age is very important for the development of children's musical abilities. In the process of musical activities, children who have certain knowledge about music, knowledge and skills join the art of music. Skills developed in the process of musical activity participate in the formation of emotional and aesthetic culture, contribute to the spiritual formation of a person.

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